

Synthesis and Antifertility Activity of 5-Oxo-5 H-Benzofuro (6, 5-C)[2] Benzopyran and Its Basic Ether Derivatives

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Synthesis and anti-implantation activity of some 9,10-diphenyl-5-oxo-5H-benzofuro (6, 5-c) [2] benzopyran and its 10-(p-alkylamino alkoxy)-phenyl derivatives are reported. The compounds have been characterized by IR, NMR and elemental analysis. Considerable anti-implantation activity is observed in a few compounds.

It is well known that furocoumarins¹ possess remarkable pharmacological properties. Tetrahydro Cannabinol², a dibenzo-(b, d)-pyran derivative possesses psychomimetic activity. Psoralen³, the well known furocoumarin prevents pregnancy in rats probably due to its estrogenic activity. In an attempt to obtain an "artificial" substitute for the scarce steroidal hormones, Dodd's⁴ group was able to find out the estrogenic activity of phenanthrene derivative; the first synthetic non-steroidal compound to be recorded. Chawla *et al*⁵ have shown that 2,3-diphenyl benzofurans possess significant anti-implantation activity. The same authors in an attempt to study the structure-activity relationship synthesized a number of related compounds. Amongst this group of compounds 2-phenyl-3-[p-(β-pyrrolidinoethoxy)-phenyl]-naphtho (2, 1-b) furan⁶, a higher homolog of 2,3-diphenyl benzofuran was found to be the most active.

Several furocoumarins (linear and angular) containing *bis* cyclic triarylethylene systems⁷, a cyclic triarylethylene system carrying simultaneously either stilbene⁸ or stilbesterol⁹ moieties in a rigid cyclic system were studied. Encouraged by the results it seemed of interest to study the effect of new furocoumarins (9,10-diphenyl-5-oxo-5H-benzofuro (6,5-c) [2] benzopyran) incorporating a phenanthrene like 6-oxo-6H-dibenzo (b, d) pyran and furan moiety with a cyclic triarylethylene system, on the fertility control.

Hydroxy coumarins needed as starting materials were synthesized by the Hurlley's¹⁰ procedure reviewed recently by Devlin¹¹. Under these conditions, with orcinol two products were obtained and they were easily separated by column chromatography, however the yield of other isomer (5-hydroxy-3,4-benzocoumarin) is about 0.4% of the total crude products. Hydroxy coumarins (2',4'-dihydroxy-biphenyl-2-carboxylic acid lactones) were then condensed with desyl chloride/4-methoxyphenyl-α-chloro-benzyl ketone to get the respective desyl ethers. They were cyclized to give linear

furocoumarin by the method reported earlier^{1,2}. The methoxy furocoumarin was demethylated using pyridine hydrochloride. The hydroxy compound obtained was condensed with hydrochlorides of various alkylaminoalkoxy/propoxychloride hydrochlorides.

5,7-Dihydroxy-3, 4-benzocoumarin (1 mole) obtained by the reaction of phloroglucinol with *o*-bromo benzoic acid was condensed with (0.5 mol) of desyl chloride and the monodesyl ether obtained, was methylated first to have a smooth alkali cyclization.

The IR spectra of furocoumarins and their predecessors, coumarinyl-*O*-desyl ethers were studied. In case of furocoumarins absorption is observed around 1700 (lactone carbonyl), 1500-1600 (strong absorption of C=C stretching) and 1500-1400 attributable to -C-O-C stretch of furan, and 800-900 assignable to furan ring breathing. In case of desyl ethers in addition to bands at 1700, 1500-1600, peaks around 1200-1300 (attributable to ether bridge) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (acyl carbonyl) were also observed.

Anti-implantation activity :

The *in vivo* anti-implantation activity of basic ether derivatives (IVa-i) were studied in adult albino rats at the Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu Tawi. In this preliminary screening female rats were treated with the drug at a dose of 10 mg/kg. The compounds were suspended in a mixture of gum acacia and distilled water. The suspension was fed orally from days 1-7 *post coitum*. The day on which the vaginal smears showed the presence of spermatozoa was considered as the day one of pregnancy. The animals were Laparotomized on day 10 of pregnancy and the number of implantation sites were recorded.

Mean number of implantation sites were calculated by adding the implantation sites in pregnant rats

and dividing them by the total number of rats treated—pregnant as well as non-pregnant. Only 80-83% inhibition of implantation was observed with few compounds at this dose level. Details are given in Table I. Among the basic ether derivatives,

(4.43 g ; 0.022 mol) and orcinol (5.0 gm, 0.040 mol) in aq. 1.5N sodium hydroxide solution (27 ml) in the general number described above, with the exception that the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 1 hr following the addition of copper sulphate solution. The crude product (1.68 gm, 33%) was crystallized from glacial acetic acid to provide (1.47 g). m.p. 159-62°.

TABLE I

Com-pound IV	Dose mg/kg i.p. (No. of animals)	%inhibition of implantation	Mean No. of implantation	%mortality during first 10 days
a	10(5)	0	9.6 ± 0.68	Nil
b	10(5)	0	9.6 ± 1.12	Nil
c	10(5)	0	9.4 ± 0.6	Nil
d	10(5)	50	4.25 ± 2.65	20
e	10(6)	33.3	6.66 ± 2.6	Nil
f	10(6)	33.3	4.3 ± 3.84	50
g	10(6)	33.3	6.0 ± 1.91	Nil
h	10(6)	83.3	1.4 ± 1.16	Nil
i	10(6)	80.0	1.8 ± 0.84	20

pyrrolidino and N, N-diethylamino groups are more active, whereas the higher homolog (piperidino propoxy) was found to be more effective than its lower homolog 'piperidino ethyloxy derivative'.

Experimental

The IR spectra were measured on Perkin-Elmer 577 and NMR on XL-100 MHz and EM. 390.90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference.

2',4'-Dihydroxy-biphenyl-2-carboxylic acid lactones. I (7-Hydroxy-3,4-benzocoumarin) :

A solution of 2-bromo benzoic acid (0.05 mol), hydroxy benzene (0.1 mol) and sodium hydroxide (0.1 mol) in water (30 ml) were heated under reflux for 30 min. A 10% aq. solution of copper sulphate (5 ml) was then added, and the mixture was heated under reflux for an additional 10 min. It was then cooled, filtered, washed well with water and dried. This material was of sufficient purity to be used as such for further preparations. The following compounds were obtained by the above route are :

Ia : 7-Hydroxy-3,4-benzocoumarin, m.p. 230-34°.

Ib : 7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-3,4-benzocoumarin, m.p. 258-60°.

Ic : 5,7-Dihydroxy-3,4-benzocoumarin, m.p. 294-302° (d).

2',4'-Dihydroxy-6'-methyl-biphenyl-2-carboxylic acid lactone : (7-Hydroxy-5-methyl-3,4-benzocoumarin) Id :

This compound was prepared by the copper catalysed condensation of o-bromo benzoic acid

Desyl ether preparation : II

The hydroxy coumarin (0.011 mol) was refluxed with desylchloride (0.01 mol) in dry acetone and potassium carbonate media for 24 hrs. The inorganic salts were filtered off, the solvent was distilled off, crude compound was obtained when treated with 1% sodium hydroxide. Crystallized the crude product from dioxane. Obtained this way are

IIa : 7-O-Desyl-3,4-benzocoumarin, m.p. 180-81°.

IIb : 7-O-Desyl-8-methyl-3,4-benzocoumarin, m.p. 218-20°.

IIc : 7-O-Desyl-5-methyl-3,4-benzocoumarin, m.p. 220-25°.

NMR (DMSO-d₆)

3.2 – three proton singlet of 5 methyl.
6.6 – one proton singlet methine proton of side chain.
8.15 – one proton singlet of 8H.
7.4-7.9 – fifteen proton multiplet aromatic protons.

II d : 5,7-Dihydroxy-3,4-benzocoumarin (2.50 gm ; 0.011 mol) was refluxed with desylchloride (2.305 gm ; 0.01 mol) and worked up as usual to get the monodesylether, m.p. 225-28°.

II e : The compound II d (4.22 gm ; 0.01 mol) and dimethyl sulfate (0.63 gm ; 0.005 mol) in acetone-pot. carbonate medium were refluxed for 24 hrs and worked up as usual to get the 7-O-desyl-5-methoxy-3,4-benzocoumarin crystallized from dioxane, m.p. 168-73°.

II f : 7-Hydroxy-3,4-benzocoumarin Ia (2.343 gm ; 0.01 mol) was also condensed with 4-methoxyphenyl- α -chlorobenzylketone (2.60 gm ; 0.01 mol) in lieu of desylchloride. On working up it gave 7-(1'-phenyl-2'-p-methoxy-phenyl-2'-oxo)-ethyloxy-3,4-benzocoumarin crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 169-70°.

Cyclization : III

Desylether (1 mol) was dissolved in minimum amount of dioxane and 0.1N aq. potassium hydroxide (3 mol) added and refluxed for 6-8 hrs. Filtered, clear filtrate was neutralized with dil. HCl to get the furocoumarin. The furocoumarins obtained this way were crystallized from dioxane.

IIIa : 9,10-diphenyl-5-oxo-5H-benzofuro (6,5-c) [2] benzopyran from (IIa), m.p. 200-202°.

IIIb : 7-methyl-9,10-diphenyl-5-oxo-5H-benzofuro (6,5-c) [2] benzopyran from (IIb), m.p. 248-50°.

IIIc : 11-methyl-9,10-diphenyl-5-oxo-5H-benzofuro (6,5-c) [2] benzopyran from (IIc), m.p. 265-70°.

IIId : 11-methoxy-9,10-diphenyl-5-oxo-5H-benzofuro (6,5-c) [2] benzopyran from (IId), m.p. 215-17°.

IIIe : 9-phenyl-10-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-5-oxo-5H-benzofuro (6,5-c) [2] benzopyran from (IIe), m.p. 230-32°.

NMR [TFA] :

3.7-three proton singlet, methoxyl.

8.1-one proton singlet 7H.

7.1-one proton singlet 11H.

7.3-7.5-thirteen proton multiplet. Aromatic protons (two side phenyl H's.+H's. of 1,2,3,4-position).

Demethylation : IV

The compound (IIIe) (3.94 g; 0.01 mol) was heated with distilled pyridine hydrochloride (11.5 g; 0.10 mol) at 230-40° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr and then mixed with water. The product on crystallization with dioxane gave 9-phenyl-10-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-oxo-5H-benzofuro (6,5-c) [2] benzopyran(IV), m.p. 288-90°.

The compound(IV) (0.01 mol) was mixed with hydrochlorides of the various bases (0.011 mol); acetone (500 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (6 gm) and the mixture was refluxed for 24 hrs. On working up the reaction mixture as usual, a solid separated that was crystallized from appropriate solvent (Table 2).

TABLE 2—BASIC ETHER DERIVATIVES OF 10-(*p*-HYDROXY PHENYL)-9-PHENYL-5-OXO-5H-BENZO FURO (6,5-C) [2] BENZOPYRAN

- (a) R=H
 (b) R=-(CH₂)₂-N(CH₂)₆
 (c) R=-(CH₂)₂-N(CH₂)₈H
 (d) R=-(CH₂)₃-N(CH₂)₆
 (e) R=-(CH-CH₂)-N(CH₂)₂-Me
 |
 CH₃
 (f) R=-(CH₂)₂-N(CH₂)₂-Me
 (g) R=-(CH₂)₂-N(CH₂)₆
 (h) R=-(CH₂)₂-N(CH₂)₄
 (i) R=-(CH₂)₂-N(CH₂)₂-Et

Com- pound	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Calculated			Found		
			C	H	N	C	H	N
a	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ O ₄	288-90	78.95	4.21	—	77.9	4.25	—
b	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ O ₅ N	120-21	76.59	5.22	2.71	75.8	5.1	2.8
c	C ₃₁ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₂ ·*HCl	279-81 (d)	75.6	5.69	5.69	74.9	5.6	5.7
d	C ₃₅ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	150-52	78.9	5.99	2.71	78.7	5.83	2.7
e	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ O ₄ N	108-10	77.42	5.81	3.01	77.45	5.8	2.95
f	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ O ₄ N	160-63	77.16	5.54	3.10	77.1	5.49	3.0
g	C ₃₃ H ₂₉ O ₄ N	155-58	78.21	5.91	2.85	79.00	5.85	2.79
h	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ O ₄ N	135-39	79.2	5.63	2.72	79.0	5.59	2.7
i	C ₃₃ H ₂₉ O ₄ N	150-53	77.6	6.05	2.92	77.0	6.0	2.89

All the melting points are uncorrected.

* Separated as salt. (Hydrochloride).

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References

1. A. MUSTAFA, FUROPYRANS and FUROPYRONES, John-Wiley, N. Y., 1961, p. 87.
2. J. LEVINE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1868.
3. V. A. POMASHENKO, *Farmakol-Alkaloidov-Glykozidov*, 1967, 266.
4. J. W. COOK, E. C. DODDS and G. L. HERWETT, *Nature*, 1933, **142**, 1121.
5. P. K. GROVER, H. P. S. CHAWLA, NITYANAND, V. P. KAMBOJ and A. B. KAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 720.

6. H. P. S. CHAWLA, P. K. GROVER, NITYANAND, V. P. KAMBOJ and A. B. KAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 54.
7. Unpublished data of the author(s).
8. B. VITTAL RAO, V. V. SOMAYAJULU, C. K. ATAL and Mrs. NIMMI CHANDHOKE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19(B)**, 220.
9. B. VITTAL RAO, V. V. SOMAYAJULU and HARISH CHANDRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19(B)**, 232.
10. W. R. H. HURTLLEY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1870.
11. J. P. DEVLIN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1975, **53(3)**, 343.
12. J. K. MACLEOD and B. R. WORTH, *Tetrahedron. Lett.*, 1972, **3**, 237.